

Office Ethics and Professionalism in the Nigerian Polytechnic System

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Abstract: Office ethics and professionalism reflect honesty, fortitude, responsibility and moral conduct in a system or organization. It is the capacity to act independently and uphold productive work practices. Like other organizations, the polytechnic system in Nigeria has its own ethical norms to guide employees in their duties. Nigerian higher education institutions like the Polytechnics have their core values that guide the conduct of their staff and students. Ethics therefore refers to the principles that guide us to make a positive impact through our decisions and actions. While office ethics refer to a set of codes, values and rules that help to determine right choices and behaviours in the office setting, professionalism means conducting oneself with responsibility, integrity, accountability and excellence. It thus means that office ethics and professionalism help an organization to achieve a common goal which is the elevation of the organization's image and reputation. The study, which is based on content analysis, is an attempt to establish a nexus between office ethics and professionalism in the polytechnic system and argues that if we are to guarantee good image and reputation for the Polytechnic system in Nigeria, there is the need for staff to be ethical and professional in the conduct of their day-to-day duties and shun unethical practices at all costs. The paper recommends among others the need for staff to strictly uphold ethical standards and professionalism in the discharge of their daily duties. This, however, can be achieved, if management is willing and ready to support the staff with the needed tools and resources to discharge their duties.

Keywords: Ethics, Behaviour, Office, Professionalism, Workplace.

1. INTRODUCTION

Office Ethics and Professionalism cover all relationships in the office or workplace. Employers seek employees who exhibit ethical and professional behaviour with regard to their manager or supervisor, their colleagues or coworkers, their customers/clients/patients and the community. Most establishments like Polytechnics regard ethics and professionalism as promoters of organization's reputation due to their direct influence on the productivity of employees and organizations. Therefore, an organization is obliged to uphold values, standards and expectations in their code of ethics. Ethics within an organization goes beyond simply abiding by rules and obeying orders. It also includes adding meaning, purpose, and a strong sense of commitment to the organizational goals. To this end, employees are rewarded due to how they adhere to the set organizational ethics. Considering the relevance of ethics and professionalism in the workplace, managements are advised to encourage staff to be ethical and professional in the discharge of their duties through fairness, clear and consistent communication, policies and procedures, transparency, training, plans of action and constructive feedback. Thus, to Zahra (2021), every organization has an ethical code that guides its decision-making and activities to have effective productivity and maintain its reputation. Ethical behaviour ensures that staff completes work with honesty and integrity and meets the aim of an organization by adhering to rules and policies. It is on this basis that this paper attempts to analyze office ethics and professionalism in the Nigerian polytechnic system with a view to establishing a nexus between both concepts.

Definition of Ethics:

Ethics is derived from the Greek word “ethos” (character) and Latin word “mores” (customs). In legal parlance, ethics defines how individuals choose to interact with one another while in educational parlance, ethics is a branch of philosophy that seeks to determine the correct application of moral notions such as “good and bad” and “right and wrong”. Ethics is also related to moral values. Adedara and Bewaji (2017) see ethics as a moral philosophy that concerns itself with the “norms of behaviour; right and wrong, good and evil, approbation and reprobation. Ethics can also be defined as “the inquiry into theories of what is good and evil and into what is right and wrong, and thus is an inquiry into what we ought and ought not to do” (Beauchamp, & Bowie, 2001). Ethics therefore refers to the principles that guide us to make a positive impact through our decisions and actions. Ethics is the discipline dealing with what is good and bad and what is right or wrong; it is the moral principles guiding behaviour in an organization. “Office Ethics” is very essential as it leads to professionalism. Wimmer and Dominick (2003) cited in Ngonso (2022) state that ethical behaviour is the “proper thing to do”. These researchers assume that someone who behaves ethically will be convinced that he has acted in a morally appropriate manner. Ethics are accepted standards of behaviour and at times preserve the integrity in the workplace. Wu (1999) asserts that ethics is “the code of moral principles that set the standard of good or bad, or right or wrong behaviour”.

Ethical behaviour therefore is characterized by honesty, fairness and equity in interpersonal, professional and academic relationships and in research and scholarly activities. Ethical behaviour is good for business and involves demonstrating respect for key moral principles that include honesty, fairness, equality, dignity, diversity and individual rights. It is thus obvious that it is more rewarding for people to indulge in ethical practices whether in office setting or outside the workplace. Staffers who get involved in unethical practices are those who have no self-control. We all have instincts but they must not be allowed to destroy us. We must cultivate self-discipline and keep our integrity intact as role models. According to Plato, “For a man to conquer himself is the first and noblest of all victories”. To Aristotle, “what lies in our power to do, lies in our power not to do”. Senior and management staffers of the polytechnic system are role models to the junior staffers they are mentoring at work on daily basis. Thus, as role models to our mentees, we must apply self-control in everything we do. As leaders, if we lose self-control, everything will fall.

What then is Office Ethics?

Before defining office ethics, it is important that we understand what an office is. According to Oxford Dictionary of Languages, **office** means “a room, a set of rooms, or building used as a place for commercial, professional or bureaucratic work. Thus, office ethics, also known as workplace ethics are the moral principles that organizations or businesses implement to determine what actions are appropriate or inappropriate at work. Office Ethics otherwise known as workplace ethics has been defined by Azowa and Tantua Jnr (2020) as a system of moral principles applied in the workplace. Office ethics provide guidelines for acceptable behaviour by organizations in both their strategy formulation and day-to-day operations. To them, an ethical approach is becoming necessary both for corporate success and a positive corporate image. Many organizations or establishments are choosing to make a public commitment to ethical workplace by formulating codes of conduct and operating principles. In doing so, they must translate into action the concepts of personal and corporate accountability, corporate giving and corporate governance (Broni, 2010 in Azowa and Tantua, 2020). Office ethics means a set of codes, values and rules that help to determine right choices and behaviours in the office setting. Code of ethics may be different depending on each office but are mostly based on the core values the office wants to express and want employee to follow.

To Schwartz, (2002), a code of ethics is a set of principles intended to guide professionals in conducting business with honesty and integrity. A code of ethics document may outline the organization’s mission and values, guide on addressing problems, establish ethical principles based on the organization’s core values, and define the standards to which professionals are held. To evaluate corporate codes of ethics ethically, you must apply universal moral standards like trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, caring, and citizenship to the stages of content, creation, implementation and administration. Adams Hayes (2024) has attempted to establish the difference between code of ethics and code of conducts. To him, a code of ethics is broader in its nature, outlining what is acceptable for the company in terms of integrity and how it operates. A code of conduct is more focused in nature and instructs how a business’s employees or a staffer of the polytechnic system should act daily and in specific situations, which links these to the values and principles of the organization

These core values of office ethics tell people how to behave. There are some office ethics that apply to almost all offices. It is usually considered wrong to take office supplies for home use, stealing, embezzlement of funds, defrauding and express rudeness on the phone or in person to client or in person to customers or to behave in any manner that violates laid down rules. These behaviours may lead to either warnings or firing, including imprisonment, depending on the abuse committed. Public and private organizations embrace office ethical practices and behaviours to increase productivity and uphold integrity while setting a penalty for workers who default workplace ethics. These office ethics are implemented by employers to foster both employee-employee relationship and employee-customer relationships. An organization may decide to put these ethics into writing or not which are meant to be followed.

Ethical behaviour in a Polytechnic system may include but not limited to the following: obeying the laws and regulations, respecting statutory rights of staff and students, not engaging in secret cult activities or be a member of secret cult, not divulging official secrets, not altering or forging official documents or aid and abet others to do same, not victimizing students for sex, ethnic, religious or personal reasons, not doing anything that will tarnish the image of the Polytechnic as well as observing copyright laws and acknowledge authors/students whenever their work is used.

Office ethics impact everything from how the system or organization is run to how employees should act at work to uphold the organization's image. Office ethics is a set of moral principles that define how an employee should behave or act at work. However, the guidelines vary depending on the organization's culture and values. A person's office ethics is a representation of his character. A strong work ethics suggests that the person places high value on doing a good job as well as respecting others and functioning with integrity (Kimberlee, 2019 in Palo, 2022). Staff with strong office ethics perform exceptionally and exhibit model professionalism which helps the organization to move forward.

Office ethics can be promoted by having leaders or managers as "role models" so that other employees under them can understand what is acceptable at work and what is not. For instance, Deans, Directors, Heads of Departments, Registrars and Deputy Registrars in the Polytechnic system in Nigeria are expected to serve as role models to students and staff under them so that they can understand what is acceptable at work and what is not even as they watch, work and take instructions from you.

Office or work ethics are moral guidelines observed by both organization and employees. For instance, when a person presents an attitude of hard-work, honesty and dedication towards his job, he is said to have a strong office or work ethic. On the contrary, failure to do so can be described as bad work ethic. Strong work ethics refers to being professional, determined, hardworking and dedicated. Staff with strong office ethic, prioritize assignments or jobs given to them, complete them on time, meet deadlines, avoid blocking the workflow and are punctual at work. These qualities make them role models to other employees in the system.

Unethical Behaviour Defined

Unethical behaviour is an action that falls outside of what is considered morally right or proper for a person, a profession, or an industry. Being unethical means one is not conforming to a high moral standard. Thus, unethical behaviour or conduct can lead to loss of job or appointment, reputation and credibility. To say someone is unethical means he or she is immoral, ruthless, corrupt, unscrupulous, unprincipled, unconscionable and a cutthroat. Ugwu (2011) refers to unethical behaviour as a behaviour that brings harm to the system and is illegal, or morally unacceptable to the larger society. By this definition, lying, corruption, cheating, stealing, divulging official secrets or interpersonal aggression would be examples of such behaviour. Although there is a legal component to ethical behaviour, it does not simply mean that because an action is not illegal that it is necessarily ethical. For instance, the action of an employee who takes longer time than necessary to do a job or who makes personal telephone calls on company time may not be considered illegal, but many people would consider one or two of them to be unethical Ugwu, 2011).

Professionalism

Professionalism does not mean wearing a suit or carrying a briefcase; rather, it means conducting oneself with responsibility, integrity, accountability and excellence. According to Pollack (2024), professionalism is more than just the need to dress appropriately (though appropriate attire certainly plays a part). Workplace professionalism is an umbrella term encompassing a spectrum of behaviours, attitudes, and communication styles that foster a positive and productive work environment. It means communicating effectively and appropriately, and always finding a way to be productive. Professionalism according to Oxford Dictionary of Languages is "the competence or skill expected of a professional. The

key to quality and efficiency is professionalism. Professionalism is the conduct, aims, or qualities that characterize or mark a professional or a professional person. Professionalism' is commonly understood as an individual's adherence to a set of standards, code of conduct or collection of qualities that characterize accepted practice within a particular area of activity".

Professionalism has to do with the way a person conducts himself or herself in the workplace. An individual who shows consideration and respect for others demonstrates a commitment to professionalism. Likewise, a person who keeps to his or her word, demonstrates loyalty, and exceeds expectation is demonstrating professionalism. Professionalism in the workplace according to Miles (2022) is when an employee: excels in the knowledge, skills and behaviours required by their role; delivers their work to the best of their abilities, even on tough days; goes above and beyond their job description; constantly looks for opportunities to grow and improve the organization – and themselves. The following are ways a person can exemplify professionalism:

1. **Being timely and punctual at work:** Being timely and punctual at work is one of the most fundamental qualities of professionalism. A professional person comes to work on time and settles in and is ready to work for the duration of work. He is punctual at appointment with clients and meetings with staff and management. He completes his work on time and he meets all deadlines given to him.
2. **Taking responsibility and being accountable:** Another quality of a professional as it relates to the polytechnic system is that he or she must be accountable for his or her actions. Someone with a high degree of professionalism takes responsibility for his assignments, and any problem that arises due to his work. If any issue arises in the course of work, a professional person must take responsibility and take action to resolve it.
3. **Being structured and well organized:** This helps him to do his job efficiently and effectively. His desk or office table is in order with only the necessary files neatly positioned for him to work.
4. **Having professional appearance and good hygiene:** People have more trust in someone who has taken the time to ensure a professional appearance. The employee who comes to work with clean clothes pressed, shirt tucked in with matching socks and hair combed, has taken his time to ensure his appearance meets the standards for his job.
5. **Being consistent and professional:** When someone has a strong office ethic, he is diligent in making sure work gets done and is done properly. Management, particularly of the polytechnic system in Nigeria wants this level of professionalism in all employees.
6. **Having humility and kindness:** A professional employee is confident and doesn't work around the office arrogantly taunting or praising his accomplishments. He is humble and kind and will offer to help others. He is a team player who understands that his contribution is one part of a bigger equation. To this end, he works with others to make sure that everyone is achieving everything he or she can.

Professional Organizations and Ethical Components

Some professional organizations may determine their ethical components as follows:

1. **Honesty:** Practice of showing strong adherence to moral and ethical principles and values such as honesty, honour, dependability and trustworthiness. People, who behave with professional integrity, generally uphold a moral standard of conduct, both as a professional and in professional endeavours.
2. **Trustworthiness:** Trustworthiness and reliability are two integral traits that serve as the foundation for successful professional relationships. Members of management of the polytechnic system should possess trustworthiness characterized by qualities such as honesty, integrity and transparency. These include being dependable, true to one's word and inspiring the confidence of others
3. **Transparency:** Office or workplace transparency between management and staff is open communication between leadership and employees at work. Leadership involves openly sharing expectations, mistakes, setbacks, feedback and other metrics. In return, employees are expected to ask questions and share feedback, challenges and ideas.
4. **Accountability:** Accountability in office or workplace include paying attention to details i.e, always ready to listen, acknowledging and fixing mistake, i.e making amends, assisting your co-workers to achieve a team work, developing a proactive approach to issues and not to wait till they degenerate, show up as a leader i.e you must be known as a leader that you are by your deeds and actions, stand up for what is right at all times, and be willing to accept criticisms

5. Confidentiality: This is called the duty of professional secrecy. This means that professionals in private or public establishments like polytechnics are not allowed to share confidential information their staff, students or clients discuss with them. This duty exists so that staff or clients can open up freely when they need help and as a professional, you must take whatever step that is necessary to address the issues.
6. Objectivity: A professional must be objective at all times in his reasoning and judgment. This is the ability to maintain a realistic perspective and keep personal biases at minimum. Leaders who are objective avoid using their own judgment and interpretation
7. Respect: This involves respect for the system, for constituted authority and for one another in the system.
8. Obedience to the Law: Professionalism demands being obedient to the laws and rules of engagement.
9. Loyalty to the system: A professional must be loyal to the system at all times

Benefits of Office Ethics and Professionalism:

According to Che-Fei Chen (2024), in today's complex and interconnected world, the importance of professional ethics cannot be overstated. These ethical standards help professionals act responsibly, honestly, and in the best interests of their clients and the public. They also provide a foundation for a well-functioning and trustworthy professional commercial environment, which benefits individuals, organizations, and society. The following are the benefits of office ethics and professionalism:

1. Promoting Collaboration and Teamwork: Office ethics and professionalism are integral in fostering increased productivity and teamwork among employees. Team players are individuals that demonstrate work ethic through teamwork. They know the system works when everyone plays his part. Workplace ethics typically encourage staff to respect one another and listen to each other's ideas. Workplace ethics and professional conduct foster an environment where collaboration and teamwork thrive. When employees trust one another's ethical behaviour, they are more likely to collaborate, share information, and support one another. Ethical conduct encourages open communication, constructive feedback, and a willingness to work together towards common goals, enhancing teamwork and fostering a cohesive and productive work environment.
2. Improved public reputation: When a system like the polytechnic system sets out for clear ethical standards and professionalism in workplace, it can basically enjoy an improved public image of the system. Code of ethics set the right culture and build a good reputation for the system. It impacts system's financial performance and attracts employees. A workplace known for its ethical practices and professionalism fosters a positive reputation. This can attract and retain talented staff. Ethics and professional conduct are essential for building trust among employees, as well as with customers, suppliers, and the broader community. When individuals consistently demonstrate honesty, integrity, and ethical behaviour, it establishes a foundation of trust. A workplace known for its ethical practices and professionalism fosters a positive reputation, which can attract and retain talented employees, loyal customers, and valuable business partnerships.
3. Maintaining a Positive Work Environment: Ethics and professional conduct contribute to a positive work culture that promotes respect, fairness, and equality. When employees adhere to ethical standards, they treat one another with respect, cooperate effectively, and contribute to a harmonious and supportive work environment. This, in turn, boosts employee morale, engagement, and overall job satisfaction, leading to increased productivity and a higher turnover rate.
4. Enhancing Decision-Making: Ethical guidelines provide a framework for making sound decisions. When faced with ethical dilemmas or complex situations, employees with a strong ethical foundation can evaluate the potential consequences and choose the most ethical and responsible course of action. Ethical decision-making promotes fairness, transparency, and accountability, ensuring that actions align with the organization's values and principles.
5. Preventing Legal and Financial Risks: Unethical behaviour in the workplace can lead to legal and financial consequences for individuals and organizations. Engaging in activities such as fraud, discrimination, harassment, or conflicts of interest can result in lawsuits, damage to the organization's reputation, and financial penalties. Adhering to ethical standards and professional conduct minimizes the risk of legal violations, protects individuals' and organizations' interests, and upholds compliance with laws and regulations.

6. Meeting Stakeholder Expectations: Ethical behaviour is increasingly important to stakeholders, including customers, investors, and business partners. They expect organizations to operate ethically, treat employees fairly, and demonstrate social and environmental responsibility. Adhering to workplace ethics and professional conduct helps organizations meet these expectations, build strong relationships with stakeholders, and enhance their brand image and reputation.
7. Personal and Professional Growth: Office ethics and professional conduct contribute to individual growth and development. By adhering to ethical standards, employees cultivate essential qualities such as integrity, accountability, and empathy. These qualities not only benefit their professional lives but also extend to personal relationships and interactions outside of work, fostering personal growth and ethical behaviour beyond the workplace.

Unethical behaviours or Conducts that should not be allowed in the Polytechnic System

Unethical and unprofessional behaviours or conducts we must avoid and prevent in our Polytechnic system as management staff and as role models include but not limited to the following:

1. Examination misconduct
2. Secret cult activities
3. Sexual harassment
4. Sales of examination grades
5. Extortions of all kinds by academic and non-academic staff
6. Falsification of data and information.
7. Lobbying for positions or appointments
8. plagiarism

Take note that indulging in these practices brings bad reputation to the individual involved and the system.

2. CONCLUSION

The study has attempted to establish a nexus between office ethics and professionalism in polytechnic system as well as other organizations. Office or workplace ethics and professional conduct play a vital role in creating a positive work environment, building trust, enhancing decision-making, mitigating risks, fostering collaboration, meeting stakeholder expectations, and promoting personal and professional growth. By prioritizing ethics and professional behaviour, the polytechnic system can establish a strong ethical foundation that drives success, employee satisfaction, and long-term sustainability. Managements of polytechnics expect its staff to be ethical and shun unethical practices in order to create a good image and reputation for the Polytechnic system. This also requires the cooperation, understanding and support of management. If management is ready and willing to support employees with necessary tools and resources, it is likely that ethical practices and professionalism will be achieved in the performance of duties in the system. Where this necessary support of the management is lacking, employees, who lack self-control and self-discipline are likely to hide under the canopy of not getting management's attention in terms of resources to work to indulge in unethical conduct. However, staff or employees must take necessary steps to live above board as anyone caught engaging in unwholesome acts will not be immune from management's sanctions.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There is need for staff of the polytechnic system to be ethical by adhering to the code of ethics as set out by the individual institutions and display professionalism at all times in discharge of their duties.
2. To achieve office ethics and professionalism in the polytechnic system, the management of the institutions must support the process by way of enforcement of rules as well as providing necessary tools and resources needed by staff to discharge their daily duties. However, where this support on the part of management is lacking, staffers, who lack self-control and self-discipline are likely to hide under the canopy of not getting management's attention in terms of tools and resources to indulge in unethical conducts or practices.

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